

Studies in thio-Claisen rearrangement : facile regioselective synthesis of 2*H*-thiopyrano[3,2-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones^{1†}

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Phase transfer catalyzed reaction of 1-alkyl-4-mercaptoquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones with different prop-2-ynylic halides afforded a number of 1-alkyl-4-prop-2-ynylthioquinolin-2(1*H*)-one derivatives. These are then subjected to heating in refluxing chlorobenzene to give hitherto unreported 2*H*-thiopyrano[3,2-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones in 85–90% isolable yields in a regioselective manner.

The Claisen rearrangement² provides a vital tool to the organic chemists for carbon-carbon bond formation^{3–8}. The importance of the Claisen rearrangement is not only due to the application for the synthesis of oxygen⁹, nitrogen¹⁰, and sulfur¹¹ heterocycles but also because of the development of several variants^{12–22} of its aliphatic counter part. The furoquinolones and pyranoquinolones are widely distributed in nature²³. They are reported to have various biological activities such as antimicrobial, antimalarial, insecticidal, antineoplastic, antidiuretic, antiarrhythmic and sedative²⁴. This wide range of biological properties has stimulated interest in the synthesis of quinolone derivatives. A number of synthesis of these heterocycles have been reported^{25,26} which also includes our own work^{27,28}. We have also reported^{29,30} the regioselective synthesis of substituted furo[2,3-*c*]quinolin-4(5*H*)-ones and 2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*c*]quinolin-5(6*H*)-ones. However, there have been no reports on the synthesis of the corresponding 3,4-fused thieno- and 2*H*-thiopyrano[3,2-*c*]quinolones. This prompted us to undertake a study on the regioselective synthesis of these heterocycles. Here we report the results of our efforts in this direction.

Results and discussion

Hitherto unreported 1-alkyl-4-mercaptoquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones (2), the starting materials for this study were synthesized by the reaction of 1-alkyl-4-chloroquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones (1) with sodium hydrosulfide in ethanol at 0–10° for 6 h (Scheme 1).

When a two phase mixture of 1-alkyl-4-mercaptoquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones (2), appropriate active halides viz. propargyl bromide, 4-chlorobut-2-yn-1-ol and 1-bromo-2-

Scheme 1

butyne (3), chloroform and 5% NaOH was stirred at room temperature in the presence of benzyltriethylammonium chloride (BTEAC), the starting material (2) disappeared within 10–12 h giving single products (TLC monitoring) 4(a-f) in 75–80% yield (Scheme 2).

	X	R	R ¹	R ²	Yield(%)
a)	Br	Me	H	H	80
b)	Br	Et	H	H	78
c)	Cl	Me	H	CH ₂ OH	80
d)	Cl	Et	H	CH ₂ OH	75
e)	Br	Me	H	Me	78
f)	Br	Et	H	Me	75

Scheme 2

Substrate 4a was refluxed in chlorobenzene (b.p. 132°) for 5 h to give a white crystalline solid, 5a, m.p. 120°. The products 4a and 5a were characterized by their elemental analyses and spectroscopic data. The IR spectra of the sul-

fide **4a** exhibited ν_{\max} at 1630–1640 cm^{-1} for the amide carbonyl function which establishes the alkylation preference for sulfur over oxygen. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **4a** showed a two-proton doublet at δ 3.8 due to SCH_2 group (J 2.5 Hz), a three-proton singlet at δ 3.7 due to NCH_3 group and triplet at δ 2.3 for the presence of terminal acetylenic proton (1H, J 2.5 Hz). Mass spectrum of **4a** showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 229 (M^+). The ^1H NMR spectrum of **5a** showed a two proton double doublet at δ 3.34 (J 6 Hz, 1.5 Hz); a three-proton singlet at δ 3.72 due to NCH_3 group, a one proton double triplet at δ 6.20 (J 10 Hz, 6 Hz); and a one proton double triplet at δ 6.85 (J 10 Hz, 1.5 Hz) indicating the formation of the six membered thiopyran ring. The formation of product **5a** was further confirmed by mass spectrum which showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 229 (M^+). Encouraged by this result, the other substrates **4(b-f)** were similarly subjected to thermal rearrangement to give the products **5(b-f)** in excellent yield (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The formation of the products **5(a-f)** from **4(a-f)** may be explained³¹ by an initial [3,3]sigmatropic rearrangement of the propynyl group to form the allene intermediate **6**. This may then undergo rapid enolization to ene-thiol **7** which is followed by [1,5]H shift to give **8** and the 6π -electrocyclic ring closure of **8** may give finally products **5(a-f)** (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Thio-Claisen rearrangement of aryl propargyl sulfides is known to give a mixture of products³², viz. 2-methylthionaphthene derivatives and 2H-thiochrom-3-ene derivatives. In some cases [1,3] Radical shifts³³ also occur when thio-Claisen rearrangements are attempted. It is highly interesting to note that in the present instance only 2H-thiopyrano derivatives are obtained, so making this methodology a regioselective synthesis.

Experimental

The melting points were recorded on a sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. UV absorption spectra were recorded in ethanol on a Hitachi 200-20 spectrometer. IR spectra were run for KBr disks on a Perkin-Elmer-FT IR spectrometer. ^1H NMR were determined for solutions in deuteriochloroform with SiMe_4 as internal standard on a Bruker 500 MHz spectrometer at the Bose Institute (Kolkata). Elemental analyses and mass spectra were recorded at C.D.R.I. (Lucknow) on a [Jeol D-300(EI)] instrument. Silica gel (60–120 mesh, Spectrochem, India) was used for chromatographic separation. Silica gel G (E. Merck, India) was used for TLC. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction boiling between 60 and 80°.

General procedure for the preparation of 1-alkyl-4-mercaptoquinolone **2** :

The 1-alkyl-4-chloroquinolone derivatives **1** (13 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) and NaSH (1.5 g, 27 mmol) was added to it at 0–10° under constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred at this temperature for 6 h. The alcohol was evaporated under reduced pressure at 40° and 1 : 1 $\text{HCl-H}_2\text{O}$ was added to it to maintain a pH ~2 when a white solid separated out. This was extracted with chloroform (2 × 50 ml) and the chloroform extract was washed with H_2O (2 × 50 ml) and dried over Na_2SO_4 . Organic layer was evaporated under reduced pressure to get 1-alkyl-4-mercaptoquinolones **2**. These were used in the subsequent reactions without further purification.

General procedure for the preparation of sulfides **4(a-f)** :

A mixture of 1-alkyl-4-mercaptoquinolin-2(1H)-one (0.57 g, 3 mmol) and propargylic halides (4.5 mmol) was taken in CHCl_3 . To it benzyltriethylammoniumchloride (BTEAC) (250 mg) in 5% aqueous NaOH (50 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10–12 h. TLC confirmed complete conversion of the starting material. It was then diluted with water (50 ml) and the aqueous layer was extracted with CHCl_3 (2 × 50 ml). The combined organic layer was washed with water (2 × 50 ml) followed by brine solution (50 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4).

Removal of solvent gave the crude gummy mass which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel (Spectrochem, India, 60–120 mesh). The pure products were obtained when the column was eluted with ethyl acetate : benzene (1 : 9). R_f 0.3 [ethyl acetate : benzene (1 : 9)].

Compound (4a) : Yield 75%; solid; m.p. 134° (Found : C, 68.34; H, 4.6; N, 5.91. $C_{13}H_{11}NOS$ requires : C, 68.12; H, 4.8; N, 6.11%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 295, 330 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3200, 2120, 1630, 1580, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 2.31 (1H, t, J 2.5 Hz), 3.7 (3H, s), 3.8 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.22–7.84 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 229 (M^+).

Compound (4b) : Yield 80%; solid; m.p. 144° (Found : C, 69.33; H, 5.51; N, 5.91. $C_{14}H_{13}NOS$ requires : C, 69.13; H, 5.34; N, 5.76%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 231, 295, 330 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3200, 2120, 1630, 1580, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 1.35 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 2.31 (1H, t, J 2.5 Hz), 3.8 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 4.33–4.37 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.21–7.84 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 243 (M^+).

Compound (4c) : Yield 75%; solid; m.p. 108° (Found : C, 64.63; H, 5.21; N, 5.23. $C_{14}H_{13}NO_2S$ requires : C, 64.86; H, 5.01; N, 5.4%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 298, 331 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3400, 2920, 1640, 1580, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 3.3 (1H, brs, exchangeable with D_2O), 3.69 (1H, s), 3.8 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 4.28 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.20–7.83 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 259 (M^+).

Compound (4d) : Yield 72%; solid; m.p. 110° (Found : C, 66.1; H, 5.69; N, 4.94. $C_{15}H_{15}NO_2S$ requires : C, 65.93; H, 5.49; N, 5.12%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 298, 331 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3400, 2910, 1640, 1580, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 1.35 (2H, t, J 7 Hz), 3.31 (1H, brs, exchangeable with D_2O), 3.8 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 4.28 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 4.33–4.37 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 6.21 (1H, s), 7.32–7.91 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 273 (M^+).

Compound (4e) : Yield 78%; solid; m.p. 132° (Found : C, 68.9; H, 5.1; N, 6.01. $C_{14}H_{13}NOS$ requires : C, 69.13; H, 5.34; N, 5.76%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 231, 298, 332 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 2920, 1630, 1580, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 1.82 (3H, t, J 2.4 Hz), 3.7 (3H, s), 3.8 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.22–7.84 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 243 (M^+).

Compound (4f) : Yield 75%; solid; m.p. 104° (Found : C, 70.25; H, 6.07; N, 5.65. $C_{15}H_{15}NOS$ requires : C, 70.03; H, 5.83; N, 5.44%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 298, 330 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 2910, 1640, 1580, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 1.35 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.81 (3H, t, J 2.4 Hz), 3.7 (3H, s), 3.8 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 4.33–4.37 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.22–7.84 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z

257 (M^+).

General procedure for the rearrangement of sulfides 5(a-f) in chlorobenzene :

Compound **4(a-f)** (2 mmol) was refluxed in chlorobenzene (5 ml) for 4–6 h. The reaction mixture was monitored by TLC. The reaction mixture was chromatographed over silica gel. Chlorobenzene was removed by eluting the column with petroleum ether (60–80°). The product was obtained when the column was eluted with benzene R_f 0.3 [benzene].

Compound (5a) : Yield 90%; solid; m.p. 120° (Found : C, 68.32; H, 5.01; N, 5.90. $C_{13}H_{11}NOS$ requires : C, 68.12; H, 4.8; N, 6.11%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 229, 350 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 2910, 1640, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 3.34 (2H, dd, J 1.5 Hz, 6 Hz), 3.72 (3H, s), 6.20 (1H, dt, J 10 Hz, 6 Hz), 6.85 (1H, dt, J 10 Hz, 1.5 Hz), 7.17–7.88 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 229 (M^+).

Compound (5b) : Yield 85%; solid; m.p. 122° (Found : C, 69.38; H, 5.05; N, 5.95. $C_{14}H_{13}NOS$ requires : C, 69.13; H, 5.34; N, 5.76%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 231, 349 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 2920, 1640, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 1.41–1.44 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 3.35 (2H, dd, J 1.5 Hz, 6 Hz), 4.46–4.5 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 6.26–6.27 (1H, dt, J 10 Hz, 6 Hz), 6.84–6.86 (1H, dt, J 10 Hz, 1.5 Hz), 7.24–7.87 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 243 (M^+).

Compound (5c) : Yield 90%; solid; m.p. 105° (Found : C, 65.03; H, 5.22; N, 5.6. $C_{14}H_{13}NO_2S$ requires : C, 64.86; H, 5.01; N, 5.4%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 232, 348 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3400, 2920, 1630, 1440 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 3.35 (2H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.77 (3H, s), 4.3 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 5.33–5.36 (1H, t, J 7 Hz), 6.06–6.08 (1H, t, J 6 Hz), 7.27–8.05 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 259 (M^+).

Compound (5d) : Yield 90%; solid; m.p. 111° (Found : C, 65.71; H, 5.3; N, 4.95. $C_{15}H_{15}NO_2S$ requires : C, 65.93; H, 5.49; N, 5.12%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 347 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3400, 2920, 1630, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 1.37–1.4 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 3.35 (2H, d, J 6 Hz), 4.3 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 4.38–4.42 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.38–5.41 (1H, t, J 7 Hz), 6.05–6.08 (1H, t, J 6 Hz), 7.27–8.04 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 273 (M^+).

Compound (5e) : Yield 82%; gummy mass (Found : C, 69.38; H, 5.14; N, 5.99. $C_{14}H_{13}NO_2S$ requires : C, 69.13; H, 5.34; N, 5.76%); UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 348 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3400, 2900, 1640, 1450 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ 2.23–2.24 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.24 (2H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.7 (3H, s), 5.76–5.78 (1H, t, J 6 Hz), 7.19–7.99 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 243 (M^+).

Compound (5f) : Yield 85%; gummy mass (Found : C,

70.24; H, 6.08; N, 5.23. C₁₄H₁₃NOS requires : C, 70.03; H, 5.83; N, 5.44%; UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 230, 348 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3400, 2900, 1640, 1450 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz) δ 1.41–1.43 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 2.21 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.2 (2H, d, J 6 Hz), 4.26–4.3 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.68–5.69 (1H, t, J 6 Hz), 7.19–7.93 (4H, m, ArH); ms m/z 257 (M⁺).

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